

The Study Of Specific Supply Chain Characteristics In Japanese Assembly Type Manufactures

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to clarify one of the competitive advantage of the distinctive supply chain management of the Japanese assembly type manufacturers have. Information Technology has been reduced both uncertainty and the complexity which global market has. It has changed a conventional paradigm, eventually to erode the strength of Japanese assembly type manufacturers generated by superiority of transaction cost and opportunity cost. The distinctive business style according to "characteristics of the Japanese" is to continue to trade the conventional subsidiary, which tries to modify a paradigm of a conventional element of competition.

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1. Introduction

The post-industrialization were simultaneous to IT oriented production and management processes which enabled and wholesale adoption and a fundamental restructuring of the manufacturing sector. These changes in finance, communications, and information transfer about the software industry, which became the economic core to globalization. In other words, globalization toward the labor, goods, services, and information transfer such as the "Capital" is dramatically very probable to improve movability. In addition, production of various elements of the "Capital" as its agility in the production or the manufacturing process can be resolved and diffused into each step globally.

On the other hand, the source of the competitiveness of the assembling type manufacturing industry in Japan was bred pre-globalization and was established until the 1980's. It is reasonable to suppose that the characteristic in quality control, production engineering and the process in the supply chain have been brought up as original corporate culture. Concretely, it has a characteristic to finish product needs, a high unification degree under an organization with high integrity and integration under the closely tied communication between affiliates. It was affairs circumstanced with the making of organizations and the employee education based on past success experiences. It is still likely that this continued as individual know-how in many companies, and the methodology in this type of process were surely dominant.

2. Background of Japanese specific supply chain system

2.1. The paradigm of the conventional competition principle

I would like to identify a background of the social modernization from the historical point of view in Japan to understand a characteristic of the activity of today's Japanese company. Regarding a digital computer in Japan, it has evolved from almost certain that solely imaged "a electric calculator" in 1960, to "the tool of the communication" between human beings in late 1980s. Practically the purpose in the network environment of human relations in the company was to be able to serve production from development of products between their own office affiliates if it is an organization before installing IT infrastructure.

"The Supply Chain" in Japan eventually produced as individual know-how in the company and it was interlocked into every individual enterprise and it is highly probable that engendered the source of the competitiveness. Besides the long-term employment system was succeeded to prevent outflow of the know-how to outside the company. The know-how in itself is limited value-added inside the company's divisions such as research and development, quality assurance and within the production engineering section.

The following graph (FIG.1) presents the most profitable business process in each Japanese company. It is shown definitely that the two most profitable processes are manufacturing and sales.

FIG. 1 vote of the most profitable business process (394 listed companies' vote)

Owning production plants inside the company facilitate, which is a strong possibility that can store their profit as internal reserve. This mechanism is a good possibility that gave them strength in the stable market, but when the market environment has frequently changed or unstable, it is a strong possibility that would be extremely hard to maintain competitiveness.

On the other hand, original know-how bred in companies was the source of the competitiveness in Japanese manufactures, It is sensitive to control outflow of these types of information, which supported conventional competitiveness with prejudice "the danger of open network environment".

On a nationwide scale, in the late 1960s quality management activities were promoted with the introduction in many companies that was carried out under the strong leader-ship of top management.

Management efforts were continued to create economic levels of high-quality products continuously under all of the members of management leading to workers, administrators.

Competitive advantage of the Japanese manufacturing industry has attributed to change the paradigm of manufacturing, to minimize cost increases, while carrying out execution of a process of moving into the high-end market segment.

The management philosophy of "you can achieve a lower cost than their competitors at the same time quality and excellence, get a competitive advantage if you can provide"

2-2. A feature of the language system involved in the thinking of the Japanese way

According to Hajime Nakamura, who is philosopher in Japan, the following items are mentioned as a feature of the language system involved in the Japanese way of thinking and social background.

1. Acceptance of reality given one.

Tend to respect the event than the theoretical. Try to understand the universal law as only in line with the special circumstances or individual basis.

2. Strong tendency to focus on human connective tissue

In addition, pronouns are complex compare to the other languages. expression of number is not strict, but in human-related representation is extremely sensitive.

3. Irrational tendency

The representation of Japanese language, tend to be emotional rather than logical sake of accuracy

It is because, a representation to avoid the conclusion, and the reason is that to consider not to hurt the emotion of the other party. Tend to not like a complex expression, loving rustic simple representation. The clutch at the complexity is possible infinitely in the simplicity. In particular, this trend can be seen in Japanese art.

In general, it is likely that the selection problem, Japanese people to understand the feelings intuitively first, such as "good" or "bad", "pleasant" or "unpleasant" and "peace of mind" or "anxiety"

It might be narrow down the number of choices as a guideline of above. It is carried out unconsciously the final judgment from the emotion heuristic. However, framing effect is thereby formed, and then a variety of cognitive bias is applied. It is reasonable to suppose that there are several cognitive biases in Japan, which define as a social trust and peace of mind, as follows.

Conservatism or Serviceability bias that means after locks up own opinion, it tends to feel information to the contrary is not suitable for oneself and ignore the information. Cognitive dissonance bias as to minimize the information untoward. In particular, unless it is bad situation, strong attraction to the status quo works.

Conformity pressure bias, which regardless of the accuracy of the objective of the contents, the situation that must be tuned to the majority.

2-3. Association with company culture trait and the profit structure in the Japanese society

According to Edward Fowler who is the researcher of Japanese literature, said, "the philosophy to accomplish things by keeping the will of the group strictly was the driving force that promoted the modernization of Japan". It is secured the unity of the group that in mind first, then a technique to plan the achievement of the composition target.

As it were, Japanese people know that self-volunteer for the group activities are better to contribute to the personal welfare than simply a working individual. These observations may appear "the commitment relations" guaranteed to continue the society based on such collectivism forever as a social background. This promotes acquisition of the human capital is effectively required to do human relations and economic relations, and call it with "the relations capital", U.S.A., Germany and Japanese society are relatively high. It occurs "to be reliable" not to mention that is fundamentally social uncertainty was reduced. Therefore, "the commitment relations" decrease social uncertainty.

Definition of "Commitment" is not to transfer immediately even if there is a good chance the other. Continuous of commitment of an investment in relationship specific assets is performed, a profit is increased by dealings with current partners. Definition of social uncertainties is the expected value of the damage caused of self-interest for the other parties, which take the self-interest pursuing. A commitment to form a relationship with a specific party, it becomes the saving of transaction cost but it will pay the opportunity cost. The opportunity cost increases gradually, a continuous to maintain commitment relationship between a specific party will be disadvantage.

The reasons are that it is an investment to relate specific assets by a mutual commitment, it is because it does not change immediately based on a deepening of mutual loyalty. This holds true for the relations of the mutual commitment for the long term even if there was a singular good opportunity in the alternative.

In social activities, trust plays an important role, especially in Japanese society. It is disadvantages to discredit particularly large. Therefore, over a long period of time trading strategy is reasonable in Japan.

3. The paradigm of competitiveness in Supply Chain system

3-1. "transaction cost" and "opportunity cost" are a competitive in Japan

Based on the pioneer achievements "essence of the company" of the Ronald .H. course (1937), Oliver .E. William loss (1975,1985) established the business cost theory, which is still evolving.

It is pointed out transaction cost occurs in the business process by all means even if it occurs between a company and organization, or within the market. Negotiation expense to complete the deal, the measurement (measurement expense) the service to trade, and carry out observance of a contract after established business.

It is defined opportunity cost as the thing which is the maximum profit that should have been provided from the different actions, as a result, it would be given up to chose a certain action. Therefore, opportunity cost is a mandatory occurrence, there is no relationship and the opportunity cost as "smaller is better", even if it does incur any judgment or choice to generate something by decision making.

To compare the expense with the profit to be provided as a result of decision making and should measure whether the judgment is proper. Consequently "transaction cost" can be saved when a company's commitments occur among the authorized partners, but to pay extra "opportunity cost".

The state of both a transaction cost and an opportunity cost are considerably low by the business relationship between inter companies in Japan, and controlled procurement of the raw materials procurement. In short, it is a way of thinking to be able to beat the competition in the market if there is production know-how to realize high quality with low cost. Transaction cost and opportunity cost advantage are a competitiveness of the distinctive supply chain in Japan.

3-2. The paradigm of Supply Chain system in the information-oriented society

In contrast of assembling type-manufacturing industry mentioned above in Japan with regard to a paradigm of the competition principle the paradigm in the information-oriented society.

1. By real time and ease of sharing characteristics of the information could create the global decentralization of the product development section, marketing method to capture a variety of local needs carefully, a product plan based on the feedback from the market.

2. Standardization of the production engineering are promoted on a global scale by the modularization of the product component. Obviously for the mass production effect, stabilization of the quality are stabilized by the modularization of the component.

3. Important social uncertainty is reduced by IT and efficient production activity which is enabled in the situation even with a short-term relation of the commitment. "The paradigm of the competition principle and the methodology" lined in a past success experience were still dominant in many Japanese companies, to promote efficiency of duties assuming maintenance of an existing framework and promoted IT restrictively.

In the network society, delay of judgment and execution delay is fatal in competitiveness.

The delay of judgment cases that require a high degree of judgment, the more time is required in organizations that require decision-making process and meeting. The delay of the execution, it is required the time until the grasp of the problem, at the same time it is highest requirement that is determined the priority.

Many of the Japanese companies still believe that quality improvement as a source of competitive advantage, trying to invest many resources in-house to further improve the quality.

By utilizing the information network, and diversification structured knowledge by information is accelerated.

On the other hand, the sharing of information in both regions who do not have knowledge about history and social culture and customs of each other, in some cases to amplify the misunderstanding of each other by the information.

It is possible to decrease the diversity of information through the communication will eliminate the complexity of the sharing of semantic information, in the reverse, expanding information lacking mutual understanding is also possible to increase complexity and uncertainty.

Idea of doing the cost down by using information technology for business processes that have been made a face-to-face business with a customer traditionally, the method of eliminating as much as possible the human intervention, it might be logically correct but if customer satisfaction decreases, it is fatal damage for the company.

4. Specificity of business model in Japanese assembly type manufacturers

4-1. IT investment characteristic of Japanese assembly type manufacturers and supplier's relationship

It is safe to say the assembling type manufacturing industry generally held the first domestic supplier and second supplier (sometimes the third, in case the fourth) in performing the last assembling process in the domestic factory, long-term with tight relationship between the companies was stable.

In addition, it is clear that the long-term relationship of mutual trust between the companies, the capital ties through the bank so-called "Keiretsu" relations maintained it. Therefore, materials and the components suppliers do not need to perform a marketing and a business development activities by themselves but to concentrate their production activity under the brand strategy of the assembled company. This business model was maintained even as assembly companies moved their plants to outside in Japan. These "Keiretsu" relations are connected by the closed system between specific companies.

The following table (Table 1.) is intended to summarize the field in IT investment by industry. It is significant that a relatively high percentage in production, accounting, sales and R&D, but in the field of logistics and procurement investment has been found to be very low in many industries.

Table 1. The most important area for IT investment by each industry

	E	M	A	F
IR	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Planning	0.0	3.1	0.0	0.0
Personnel	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0
Procurement	2.8	9.2	0.0	0.0
Logistics	7.0	1.5	4.3	0.0
R&D	16.9	7.7	47.8	16.7
Sales	14.1	7.7	4.3	16.7
Accounting	14.1	16.9	8.7	16.7
Manufacturing	25.4	41.5	21.7	27.8

(%)

E: electronics M: machinery

A: automobile F: fine mechanics

It is highly probable that the decline of the competitiveness of the assembling type manufacturing industry in Japan depends on "status quo bias" that is going to maintain the paradigm of the conventional competition principle, continuing works of each company's and/or internal divisions' relationship. This is a strong possibility that logistics and procurement process were strong influences of status quo bias and is eventually suggested very probable that it is a result of dominance of conventional paradigm thought.

4-2. Japanese assembly manufacturers and their suppliers' supply chain framework

Regarding a formation process for Japanese distinctive supply chain framework as "Keiretsu", the company activity focuses on financial resources into adapting themselves to new environment for the purpose of increasing profits. After the formation of "Keiretsu" is established, a frame of business hardens and then it prescribes company activity as the most effective management method. Between initial process manufactures (or the upper part of companies) and final process manufactures (or the lower part

of companies) develop interdependence, and the immobilization (inter-mingling) of the supply chain is planned. These relations are maintained unless a big change or paradigm shift occurs in the external environment. It is likely that this situation is Nash equilibrium, and this state is stable as far as economy moves smoothly.

FIG. 2 “Keiretsu” and “non-Keiretsu” portion, comparisons to change the relationship

Above FIG.2 shows this phenomenon. The first bar chart is the data listed companies as suppliers in Japan, indicating affiliation, “Keiretsu” or “non-Keiretsu”. In 2004, 50% shows a series of procurement from outside as “non-Keiretsu”.

However, the next bar chart shows the change in affiliation in comparison with 10 years ago, as a supplier, As shown in this graph, it have responded series together, “Keiretsu” or “non-Keiretsu”, and has not changed more than 70%. It is appropriate to show a state of long-term commitment.

4-3. The reasons of many Japanese manufacturers stays in conventional system

As for most of Japanese companies, "Keiretsu" became the model by longtime trade practice as I looked in 4-2. and bred the relationship that strengthened each other's relationships based on the mutual trust. That raises the possibility of production and design in-house, but it is with the product design that accepts the specifications that the customer specified and confirmed by the build-to-order manufacturing.

The internal mechanism of components may be the supplier’s technology, but the outside specifications such as form factor, interfaces will accept a demand of the assembly manufacture as a customer. From a strong relationship of mutual trust, it becomes the tacit rule mutually in Japan that the build-to-order manufacturing obeys customer specifications. "Production with possibility" have many products for general consumers, and electronics appliance in home use and a product of the assembling type manufacturing industry including the car manufactures, a lot of part makers and components supplier are related under one vehicle maker in the automotive industry. The electronics appliance is similar.

The following graph (FIG.3) shows the reason for an increase in trading partners, “Keiretsu” or “non-Keiretsu”, there was rationale for cost reduction and improved quality, making it similar proportions in both. In “Keiretsu”, there are a large proportion with leakage of know-how and information, internal “non-Keiretsu, to cope with high-mix and low-volume production and prompt delivery. These 2 issues are highly connected and reflected the cost. This statistics is remarkable in any industry.

FIG. 3 the reason for an increase in trading partners, “Keiretsu” or “non-Keiretsu”

A production system is a mechanism to convert demand information into product supply, and an aim of the production control is to synchronize demand and production. Theoretically it can start from the settled demand by the build-to-order manufacturing, the stock becomes minimal. That is why the part maker as suppliers were thought to be typical repetition build-to-order manufacturing, but the real situation did not need to be fixed at a timing either production of the quantity of delivery until the expansion of the market just before it in today and cannot cope by production with possibility.

On the other hand, the resale to the other companies is not possible because a part is a customer specifications product. Therefore the company will continue holding certain parts as dead stock if the reading of the demand prediction is not successful. This is because the production schedule of the end product manufacturers reaching the hand of consumers' uncertainty, the environment of the market changes frequently, depending on fluctuating demand, they would like to change a plan at anytime, but this is because the situation that the risk hedge therefore to have part stock by themselves. Above all, a given supplier has to produce their own stock as their own forecast, which would be occurred "the waste of surplus produces" in supplier side.

5. Conclusion

To sum up the major characteristics of Japanese assembly manufacturers, Japanese supply chains characteristics have strongly relevance Japan's traditional society that have been cultivated Japanese language and way of thinking, but it was surely competitive advantage until late 1980.

A further important point is an essential problem the product in each country to understand the market well that consumers are able to accept what price range by what kind of function, it is required to continue to build a supply chain model that unified engineering, manufacturing, and sales. Even selling in the same product is depending by the market, the distribution of preferences in each market. It is because different consumer-oriented functional, quality-conscious and consumer price preference therefore supply chain system should focus on it. It has changed significantly the relationship between consumption and production of the entire society by the information technology, to comply with it, it is essential to share information under the construction of organization and management for suppliers.

It is concluded that Information Technology made a paradigm shift of supply chain management therefore Japan has to adapt this situation as soon as possible.

There is "the principle of smallest various degrees" of William R. Ashby that is necessary for a system to adopt variety is to adapt to an environmental change. The theory mentioned has to increase variety of the system control to protect a system border from the environment changes. In other words, only various degrees of diversity can reduce various degrees of the environmental noise. It is to raise various degrees inside rather than the environmental diverseness degree. It should be pointed out diversity can help to deal with various environmental changes, that is the system survives, various degrees can utilize various resources towards that purpose. If the diversification does not exist inside an organization, then a person with of a variety of sense of values and skills must be taken from the outside and integrated to, then to upgrade those connections. The diversification of the supply chain that is the globalization brought complexity and the uncertainty that the market had changed. IT was implemented to overcome this phenomenon. Many Japanese companies promoted IT for the efficiency in the existing framework. Therefore IT system in Japan remains in information sharing for the closed internal of company and Keiretsu appearance. Moreover, it was one of the triggers that the delay of the correspondence to Internet environment focused on a negative effect too much.

As the result, the innovation of the market accepts by raising the diversity of each company. The Japanese assembly manufacturers' supply chain system should be modified for each market conformance and competitiveness. Even then, it is not solely to shift IT centric system by abdicating Japanese traditional one. The future direction of this study will be how to harmonize various traditional Japanese system based on IT infrastructure rapidly in today's global market competition.

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